

Project:
NANOFACTS
 Grant Agreement (GA) No. 952259

“NETWORKING ACTIVITIES FOR NANOTECHNOLOGY-FACILITATED CANCER
 THERANOSTICS”

Call: H2020-WIDESPREAD-2020-5

Topic: WIDESPREAD-05-2020 - Twinning

Type of action: CSA - Coordination and support action

D6.4: NANOFACTS Webportal, and Social Media Groups

Start date of project: 01/01/2021

Duration: 36 months

Document History
(Revisions – Amendments)

Version and date	Changes
1.1. 07/04/2021	Nikola Knežević (PC)

Dissemination Level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the EC Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the EC Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the EC)	

This report includes information about the NANOFACTS Webportal and Social media groups, established to promote NANOFACTS activities.

NANOFACTS Webportal is registered since **19.02.2021**. and the hosting is arranged for the period of 3 years, at the following URL: <http://nanofacts.net>

The design of the Webportal is to be significantly improved, as the new version of the Webportal is in preparation, which will include separate pages for the NANOFACTS activities, publications, scientific information on the relevant research topics, as well as to introduce the NANOFACTS consortium and research teams.

Social media groups for NANOFACTS are registered since **03.02.2021**. at the following social media:

FACEBOOK; Link: <https://www.facebook.com/nanofacts2020>

Linkedin; Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/nanofacts>

Instagram; Link: https://www.instagram.com/_nanofacts/

Twitter; Link: <https://twitter.com/NANOFACTS2>

The dissemination through these social media groups started on February 4th 2021., with the information about the Kickoff meeting. Further dissemination of NANOFACTS activities is ongoing.

All these dissemination channels present a knowledge repository and communicator to promote project activities and results.

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